

Chitosan-Graphene Oxide Composite Membrane for Fouling Reduction in Ultrafiltration

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Extended Abstract

One of the major challenges in wastewater treatment using ultrafiltration is the membrane fouling caused due to deposition of pollutants on the membrane surface during the filtration process. Most of the time the fouling can be reversed easily by simple back wash, however, some of the pollutants can form covalent bond with the membrane surface and cause irreversible fouling (Singh, 2015). Irreversible membrane fouling can be mitigated by increasing membrane hydrophilicity (Singh, 2015). The fouling propensity of a membrane can be reduced by incorporating hydrophilic functional groups in the membrane matrix.

Chitosan (CH) contains an abundance of amide and hydroxyl functional groups. However, chitosan does not dissolve in membrane casting solution which results in non-uniform pore distribution and larger pore radius. On the other hand, graphene oxide (GO) has been extensively used for improving membrane hydrophilicity owing to existence of hydroxyl and carboxylic functional group in their structure (Zinadini et al., 2014). Moreover, graphene oxide has been found to provide better anchor points for the nanomaterials and prevent nanoparticle leaching during filtration (Zinadini et al., 2014).

Thus, in this paper, GO has been functionalized with CH and has been used as nanofiller for a polysulfone (Psf) membrane with the aim of improving the anti-fouling properties of the Psf membrane.

The GO used in this study has been synthesized using modified Hummer's methods, previously used by Mahmoudi et al. (2015) (Mahmoudi et al., 2015). The CH was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. In order to functionalize GO with CH, appropriate amount of CH was dissolved in 10 v/v% acetic acid at room temperature. Then appropriate amount of GO was added to the solution and stirred gently for 1 day. The resultant solution was cleaned with water and ethanol and dried in an oven at 60°C. The dried sample was then characterized using FTIR spectroscopy using SHIMADZU FTIR-8400S.

The membrane casting solution was prepared by adding appropriate amount of CH functionalized GO and polysulfone in N-Methyl Pyrrolidone. The quantity of different components in the casting solution can be seen in Table 1. The membranes were fabricated by

44 the phase inversion method. The fabricated membranes were tested using a stirred cell
45 (Sterlitech HP4750). A flat sheet membrane with surface area of 14.6 cm² was inserted at the
46 bottom of the stirred cell and the membrane was compacted for 20 mins before a transmembrane
47 pressure of 4 bar was applied to study water permeability. The pure water permeation flux
48 ($J, L/m^2h$) was calculated as:

$$J = \frac{\Delta V}{A\Delta t} \quad (1)$$

49 Here, ΔV , Δt and A represents accumulated volume of permeate (L), filtration time (h) and
50 effective membrane area (m²), respectively. The membrane resistance (R_m, m^{-1}) has been
51 evaluated as:

$$R_m = \frac{\Delta P}{\mu J} \quad (2)$$

53 Here, ΔP and μ represents transmembrane pressure (Pa) and dynamic viscosity of water (Pa s),
54 respectively. The porosity ($\epsilon, \%$) of the membranes were determined using the gravimetric
55 method and is evaluated as:

$$\epsilon = \frac{\omega_1 - \omega_2}{Ald_w} \quad (3)$$

56 Here, ω_1 , ω_2 , l and d_w represents mass of wet membrane (gm), mass of dry membrane (gm),
57 thickness of the membrane (mm) and density of water (kg/m³), respectively. Using the porosity
58 data and Guerout–Elford–Ferry equation, the pore size was estimated as (Mahmoudi et al.,
59 2015):

$$r_m = \sqrt{\frac{(2.9 - 1.75\epsilon)8\eta l Q}{\epsilon A \Delta P}} \quad (4)$$

60 Here, Q , and η represents volumetric flowrate of the permeate (m³/s) and viscosity of water (Pa
61 s), respectively. The membrane hydrophilicity was measured in terms of the contact angle
62 measured by DataPhysics contact angle analyzer (OCA15 Pro, Germany).

63 The membrane fouling study was carried out using 2000 ppm of Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA)
64 solution. During the fouling study, three filtration cycles were carried out. The initial pure water
65 permeate flux (J_0), BSA solution permeation flux (J_f) and pure water permeate flux after
66 cleaning (J_1) was used to evaluate the flux recovery ratio ($FRR\%$), total fouling ratio ($R_t\%$),
67 irreversible fouling ratio ($R_{ir}\%$) and reversible fouling ratio ($R_r\%$). These parameters were
68 calculated as:

$$FRR(\%) = \frac{J_1}{J_0} \times 100\% \quad (5)$$

$$R_t(\%) = \frac{J_0 - J_f}{J_0} \times 100\% \quad (6)$$

$$R_{ir}(\%) = \frac{J_0 - J_1}{J_0} \times 100\% \quad (7)$$

$$R_r(\%) = \frac{(J_1 - J_f)}{J_0} \times 100\% \quad (8)$$

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Table 1. Composition of the fabricated membranes.

Membranes	NMP (wt%)	Psf (wt%)	GO (wt%)
GC-0	83	17	0
GC-1	83	17	0.034
GC-2	83	17	0.085
GC-3	83	17	0.136

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* Weight based on the weight of Psf

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75 The functionalization of the GO with CH has been confirmed by FTIR analysis shown in Figure
 76 1. In Figure 1, the peak observed at 3474 cm^{-1} corresponds to the stretching of amide and
 77 hydroxyl groups and the peak at 1062 cm^{-1} corresponds to the C-O stretching vibration. The
 78 band at 1643 corresponds to the acylated units. The higher intensity of the observed peaks at
 79 different GO-CH loading ratios confirms the functionalization of GO by CH.

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Figure 1. FTIR of the synthesized nanoparticles.

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83 Table 2 shows the membrane resistance, porosity, pore radius, contact angle and flux of the
 84 fabricated membranes. As seen from the Table 1, the lowest membrane flux of 3.55 LMH/bar
 85 can be seen for GC-3 and the highest membrane flux of 9.66 can be seen for GC-2. The lowest
 86 and highest pore radius in GC-2 and GC-3 (9.84 nm and 12.28 nm, respectively) is
 87 responsible for the respective observed fluxes. The highest contact angle of 90.36° in Table 2
 88 can be seen for the pristine Psf membrane (GC-0). All other membranes showed lower
 89 contact angle, thus confirming improvement of hydrophilicity of the polysulfone membranes
 90 after incorporation of CH functionalized GO in the membrane matrix.

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Table 2. Properties of the fabricated membranes.

Membrane	Resistance	Porosity (%)	Pore radius (nm)	Contact angle (°)	Flux (LMH/bar)
GC-0	17.35	17.85	11.41	90.36	6.23
GC-1	22.55	16.1	10.35	84.19	6.53
GC-2	22.25	11.6	12.28	81.02	9.66
GC-3	13.52	31.62	9.84	75.16	3.55

94 Figure 2 shows the effect of GO loading on the pore radius and membrane flux. As seen in
 95 Figure 2, increasing the GO wt% (at 1:0.5 GO:CH ratio) from 0 wt% to 0.085 wt% increases
 96 the water permeability flux. This is because of the increasing pore radius with increasing GO
 97 wt%. Moreover, the reduction in hydrophobicity is also responsible for this increment.
 98 However, increasing the GO wt% above 0.085 wt% reduced the pore radius and resulted in the
 99 reduction of membrane flux.

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102 Figure 2. Effect of GO (at 1:0.5 GO:CH) loading on pure water permeability flux.

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104 Table 3 shows the flux recovery, total fouling, irreversible fouling and reversible fouling of the
 105 fabricated membranes. As seen from Table 3, the pristine membrane (GC-0) has the lowest flux
 106 recovery & reversible fouling, and highest irreversible fouling. Whereas, GC-3 has the highest
 107 flux recovery and one of the lowest irreversible fouling. GC-3 has exhibited a contact angle of
 108 75.16° which is the lowest among the fabricated membranes. The improvement in the fouling
 109 parameters can be attributed to the enhanced hydrophilicity of the GC-3 membrane.

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Table 3. Fouling parameters of the fabricated membranes.

Membrane	Flux recovery (%)	Total fouling (%)	Irreversible fouling (%)	Reversible fouling (%)
GC-0	61.89	76.04	38.10	37.94
GC-1	79.51	24.61	20.48	4.12
GC-2	81.61	69.41	18.38	51.03
GC-3	93.67	53.64	6.32	47.31

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112 The results indicated that incorporation of CH functionalized GO can improve the water flux
113 and anti-fouling properties of the polysulfone membrane.

114 **Conclusions**

115 By incorporating chitosan functionalized graphene oxide, the number of hydrophilic functional
116 groups were increased in the polysulfone membrane matrix. This resulted in increased
117 hydrophilicity and pore size of the synthesized membranes. The increasing pore size enhanced
118 water flux and the increased hydrophilicity improved the flux recovery, total fouling,
119 irreversible and reversible fouling of the synthesized polysulfone membranes.

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